

Determination of the Titer of Antibodies against Endotoxins of Gram-Negative Bacteria in Diseases of Various Microbial Etiology and Evaluation of its Diagnostic Value

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Abstract: *Detection of antibodies against bacterial endotoxins is an important diagnostic method for evaluating the immune response against infections, and their clinical significance is high. Endotoxins (LPS - lipopolysaccharides) are part of the bacterial cell membrane and activate the immune system to cause disease in the body.*

Key words: *LPS, endotoxin, gram-negative bacteria, organotrope, pyrogen.*

Endotoxins are a complex of proteins and lipopolysaccharides (LPS) found in the cell wall of gram-negative bacteria. They differ from protein toxins by their lack of organotropy and non-specific effects [4, 5].

All groups of their molecules are responsible for the biological effect of endotoxins of gram-positive bacteria [1, 2, 3].

A small amount of endotoxins of representatives of gram-negative bacteria of the normal microflora of the large intestine has an antigen-stimulating effect on the immune system, strengthens the non-specific resistance of the human body, and increases the anti-tumor activity of cells [8, 10].

Antiendotoxin immunity in diseases of various microbial etiology in children, specific properties of endotoxin (pyrogenic effect, bleeding and activation of intravascular thrombus formation, hemodynamic disorders, enhancement of the immune humoral system, impaired kidney function, weak immunogenic effect) and are associated with the features of the pathogenesis of these diseases.

The purpose of the study was to determine the titer of antibodies against endotoxins of gram-negative bacteria in children with various microbial etiology and to evaluate its diagnostic value.

Research materials and methods. In order to achieve the goal, blood sera of children with acute tonsillitis, acute bronchitis and urinary tract infections, which are common among children living permanently in our region, were studied. 251 sick children aged 3-14 years living in the Khorezm region of Uzbekistan were involved in the research, 87 of them were diagnosed with acute tonsillitis, 71 with acute bronchitis, and 93 with urinary tract infections (UTIs). All these patients were grouped into the main group as diseases of microbial etiology (MEK).

In order to compare the obtained results, the blood serum of 25 practically healthy children (1 - comparison group) and 61 children with colon dysbiosis (YID) (2 - comparison group) were examined. All groups were representative in terms of age-sex composition.

Children under 3 years of age were not included in the study, taking into account the immaturity of the immune system in early-aged children, the absence of "positive" and "false-positive" reactions [6] due to the short duration of antigen stimulation. All children were divided into age groups: 3-6 years old (preschool period) and 7-14 years old (school period).

All diagnoses were made using the 10th revised International Classification of Diseases (ICD, 1997). Ethical principles related to the involvement of children in medical research were implemented based on the Helsinki Declaration of the World Medical Association (Helsinki, 1964, last updated Seoul, 2008).

The concentration of anti-endotoxin antibodies against the cell wall LPS of examined children's blood serum was determined by the IFA method using an experimental test system on recommended 96-well tablets [6, 7]. Microorganism cultures used to obtain microbial antigens were obtained from the National Collection of Microorganisms of Human Infections UzR SSV EMYuK ITI (2006, No. 2 contract). Collection strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiellae pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were used in the scientific work. They were used in the form of a solution of inactivated bacteria at a concentration of 1×10^9 microbial bodies /ml. Microbial antigens were isolated according to Buaven by extracting day cultures of bacteria in trichloroacetic acid.

Statistical processing of the results was carried out using generally accepted methods for medical and biological research. The studies and their conclusions were conducted based on the principles of evidence-based medicine.

Results obtained and discussion. It is known that one of the etiological criteria of Gram-negative conditionally pathogenic bacteria (GShPB) is the detection of antigens of microorganisms in blood serum, specific antibodies to their endotoxin [3]. Based on this, the titer of antibodies against GShPB antigens was determined in the first part of our study.

The titer of specific antibodies against GShPB antigens in the blood serum of most of the examined children with MEK and IID was determined to be reliably higher ($R < 0.001$) compared to these indicators of healthy children. Antibody detection level depended on nosological units and microorganism type ($R < 0.001$).

Percentage of detection of antibodies against *Escherichia coli* (88.0%, $n=221$), *Citrobacter freundii* (79.3%, $n=199$) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (70.2%, $n=176$) antigens in children diagnosed with MEK *Proteus vulgaris* (56.2%, $n=141$) and *Klebsiellae pneumoniae* (51.4%, $n=129$) were significantly higher than the titer of antibodies against antigens ($R < 0.05$). A higher percentage of seropositive samples for *Escherichia coli* antigens in children diagnosed with MEK is associated with greater detection of antibodies in SYI.

A similar trend was observed in children diagnosed with IID: *Escherichia coli* - 80.3% ($n=49$); *Citrobacter freundii* - 52.5% ($n=32$); *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* - 39.3% ($n=24$); *Proteus vulgaris* - 59.0% ($n=36$) and *Klebsiellae pneumoniae* - 41.0% ($n=25$). The difference was in the detection percentage of antibodies against *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* antigens.

Thus, the percentage of antibodies against GShPB antigens in blood serum was reliably higher in children with MEK than in both comparison groups. When micro-organisms were compared to each other, the percentage of detection of antibodies was higher for *Escherichia coli*, *Citrobacter freundii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in healthy children diagnosed with MEK, and for *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Citrobacter freundii* antigens in children with IID.

The comparison of seropositive and seronegative samples between groups revealed the following: healthy children had significantly more seronegative samples compared to other groups ($R < 0.001$); In children with MEK and YID, seropositive samples at different titers were statistically different compared to comparison group 1 ($R < 0.001$). This condition can be explained by an increase in the concentration of microbial antigens in the blood serum when diseases and dysbiosis are observed, respectively, by a high titer of antibodies.

The next part of the study was devoted to the assessment of antiendotoxin immune status in examined patients and healthy children.

The obtained results showed that the level and titer of antibodies to GShPB endotoxins depended on the nosological unit, the body condition and the age of the examinees. Therefore, we found it necessary to describe the age groups (3-6 years and 7-14 years) separately.

A positive titer of antibodies to GShPB endotoxins (seropositive samples) was detected in $10.0 \pm 6.9\%$ of healthy children aged 3-6 years (Table 1), with increasing age of children (Table 2), positive results decreased ($6.7 \pm 4, 8\%$), but no significant difference was observed between the numbers ($R > 0.05$). Differences in the detection of antibodies against GShPB antigens in practically healthy children were different from the results obtained by some researchers [9].

Table 1 Detection percentages of seropositive samples in the blood serum of 3-6-year-old patients and healthy children

G groups	Indicators, %
Comparison group 1 (1 in 10 positive)	$10.0 \pm 6, 9$
Comparison group 2 (15 positive out of 20)	$75.0 \pm 5, 1 *$
Main group - MEK (88 positive out of 97)	$90.7 \pm 2.4 *$

Appendix: * - 1 - reliable difference from the comparison group.

Indicators among children diagnosed with IID differed reliably compared to healthy children, the level of antiendotoxin antibodies was determined in $85.4 \pm 3.9\%$ of the examined. Detection of antibodies against GShPB endotoxins in children with MEK reached $90.7 \pm 2.4\%$, which was significantly higher than the values of both comparison groups ($R < 0.001$ and $R < 0.05$, respectively).

With increasing age of subjects, the percentage of detection of antibodies increased in the main group and in the 2nd comparison group, although not reliably ($R > 0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 2 Detection percentages of seropositive samples in the blood serum of patients and healthy children aged 7-14 years

G groups	Indicators, %
1 - comparison group (1 positive out of 15)	$6.7 \pm 4, 8$
2 - comparison group (35 positive out of 41)	$85, 4 \pm 3, 9 *$
Main group - MEK (137 positive out of 154)	$89.0 \pm 2.3 *$

Appendix: * - 1 - reliable difference from the comparison group.

It was found that the detection level of antiendotoxin antibodies in children's blood serum depends on the age of the examined children, the development of IID in children, the diagnosed nosological unit and the type of GShPB.

In order to identify the nosological unit that has a greater influence on the indicators of the main group, we performed a comparative analysis of MEK parameters by diseases.

The obtained results showed that the highest indicators of detection of antibodies against endotoxin were found in children aged 3-6 years with SYI, and were reliably different not only from the comparison groups ($R < 0.001$), but also from the indicators of children diagnosed with acute tonsillitis and acute bronchitis (Table 3).

Table 3 Detection of anti-endotoxin antibodies in blood serum of 3-6-year-old children by nosological units comparative indicators, %

G groups	Indicators, %
1 - comparison group, n=10	10.0 ± 6, 9
2 - comparison group, n=20	75.0 ± 5, 1 *
Acute tonsillitis, n=2 1	76.2 ± 3.1 *
Acute bronchitis, n=2 8	89.3 ± 2.7 *
Urinary tract infections, n=20	95.0 ± 2.4 *

Appendix: * - 1 - reliable difference from the comparison group.

We observed a similar trend in the studied 7-14-year-old children, although the numbers are different (Table 4).

Thus, the indicators of detection of antibodies against GShPB antigens in children with MEK and IID were reliably different from the parameters of healthy children, but when compared to each other, a reliable difference was found in 3-6-year-olds ($R < 0.05$), and no statistical difference was observed in 7-14-year-olds ($R > 0.05$). In terms of nosology, a reliable difference from the 1st and 2nd comparison groups was observed in acute bronchitis and SYI in 3-6-year-olds, and in 7-14-year-olds such a difference was found only in SYI.

Table 4 Comparison of antiendotoxin antibody detection in blood serum of 7 - 14-year-old children by nosological units indicators, %

G groups	Indicators, %
1 - comparison group, n=1 5	6.7 ± 4, 8
2 - comparison group, n= 41	85.4 ± 3.9
Acute tonsillitis, n= 66	83.3 ± 2.9
Acute bronchitis, n= 43	90.7 ± 2.9
Urinary tract infections, n= 73	97.3 ± 2.0

Appendix: * - 1 - reliable difference from the comparison group.

After conducting a comparative assessment of the level of detection of antiendotoxin antibodies, there was a need to compare the intensity of their formation. In order to facilitate the description of the obtained results, antitoxin antibodies were divided into groups based on the intensity (titer) of formation: "negative" (titer was not detected); "low" (title 1:2 - 1:8); "medium" (title 1:16 - 1:64); "high" (titer 1:128 and higher) titers [9].

The obtained results showed that the titer of antibodies in blood serum of 3-6 - year-old healthy children (comparison group 1) was "negative" in most cases ($90.0 \pm 7.8\%$) (Table 5).

The intensity of antibody detection in MEK was significantly different compared to the comparison groups. There was no difference in MEK among 3 - 6-year-old children with IID in the percentage of antiendotoxin antibody detection, but the difference in intensity was evident.

We observed the same indicators in 7-14-year-old children (Table 6).

Table 5 Indicators of intensity of formation of anti-endotoxin antibodies in blood serum of 3-6-year-old children, %

G groups	"Negative"	"low"	"Medium"	"High"
1 - comparison group, n=10	90,0 ± 7,8	10,0 ± 6,9	0	0
2 - comparison group, n=20	25.0 ± 6.4 *	75.0 ± 8,6*	0	0
Acute tonsillitis, n= 21	23,8 ± 5,1*	19.0 ± 4.7 *	28,6 ± 4,9	28,6 ± 4,9
Acute bronchitis, n= 28	10.7 ± 6.8 *	17.9 ± 3,8*	35,7 ± 3.6	35,7 ± 3.6
SYI, n= 73	5.0 ± 2.5*	10.0 ± 2.5 *	25,0 ± 2,5	60,0 ± 2,0

Application: * - 1 - reliable difference from the comparison group.

Table 6 Indicators of intensity of formation of antiendotoxin antibodies in blood serum of 7 - 14-year-old children, %

G groups	"Negative"	"low"	"Medium"	"High"
1 - comparison group, n=15	93,3 ± 3.1	6,7 ± 4,8	0	0
2 - comparison group, n=41	14.6 ± 4.2 *	85,4 ± 3,9*	0	0
Acute tonsillitis, n= 66	16.7 ± 3.7 *	24,2 ± 3,1*	28,8 ± 3,5	30,3 ± 3,1
Acute bron hit, n= 43	9,3 ± 4,9*	20.9 ± 4.5 *	27,9 ± 4.4	41,9 ± 4.1
SYI, n= 73	2.7 ± 1.9*	16.4 ± 2.6 *	28,8 ± 2,5	52,1 ± 2,2

Application: * - 1 - reliable difference from the comparison group.

It can be seen that in this age group, the trend of changes in indicators of 3 - 6 year old children is preserved.

Thus, a clear and convincing difference was found in MEK (acute tonsillitis, acute bronchitis, and SYI) parameters in terms of the intensity of antibody formation against GShPB endotoxins compared to both comparison groups. There were no differences in the trend of changes between age groups.

Conclusions.

1. The percentage of seropositive sera for GShPB antigens was reliably higher in children with MEK and IID compared to healthy children. The percentage of detection of antitoxin antibodies depended on the type of microorganism.
2. The percentage of detection of antitoxin antibodies in blood serum was statistically higher in children with SYI compared to other compared pathological conditions.
3. MEK significantly differed from comparison groups in intensity (titer) of antitoxin antibody formation. In MEK, mainly "medium" and "high" titers were detected, while only "low" titers were detected in healthy and IID children.
4. Determination of the intensity of formation of antibodies against GShPB endotoxins in "medium" and "high" titers can be used as an additional diagnostic and prospective criterion in the diagnosis of MEK.

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